

Spatial Relationship Criterion #5: Points On Polylines

This criterion is particularly useful for analyzing the spatial relationship between point features and polylines, helping to determine whether specific points are directly on or along a polyline feature.

In this practical example, we'll work with point data gathered through field measurements for the maintenance of a telecommunications network, specifically focusing on underground optical cable pipelines. The scenario involves an optical cable network, where each shapefile represents a different cable segment. The point coordinates represent the actual field data collected for maintenance purposes.

Our task is to overlay these points onto the network and identify which points align with specific cable segments. Let's explore how this process is carried out using SGIS Desktop.

All the shapefile layers have been imported into the software, but they are initially disabled. To provide a clearer view of the cable segments, we'll enable them one by one. In Fig.1, two cable segments are now visible in the Graphics panel.

Fig.1 Two cable segments are displayed on the Graphics panel after selectively enabling the relevant shapefile layers for clearer visualization.

Next, we'll continue enabling each layer one by one until all five cable segments are visible. Each segment is color-coded differently for easy distinction.

Finally, we'll enable the point layer containing the field measurement data.

Fig.2 Three optical cable segments, each distinguished by unique colors, are now enabled and visible on the Graphics panel for easier identification.

Fig.3 All five optical cable segments are now enabled and visible on the Graphics panel, while the point data remains disabled.

The point data consists of measurements taken along the trench of the telecommunications network, with additional points for segments that aren't currently displayed. All of this data is stored in a single CSV file, rather than being divided by segments.

As shown in Fig.4, there are a large number of points to work with, so we need the quickest and most efficient way to sort these points by their respective segments.

Fig.4 A large number of point data is displayed on the Graphics panel, highlighting the need for a quick and efficient method to sort these points by their respective cable segments.

The 'Select by Layer' tool, specifically the 'Points On Polylines' option, offers a quick solution that saves us the hassle of manually drawing polygons around each cable segment to isolate points. Instead, we can easily set our selection mode and criteria—for instance, finding the points that fall directly on Segment 1.

So, let's start with the first segment: We begin by opening the 'Select by Layer' function.

Fig.5 The 'Select by Layer' function is opened, ready to configure the selection for the first segment of the optical cable network.

Next, we select the "Points On PolyLines" option from the dropdown list and click on it to proceed.

Fig.6 The "Points On PolyLines" option is selected from the dropdown menu.

Next, we move to the second dropdown menu and select the Point layer, since that's where we want to choose the points for our analysis.

Fig.7 The second dropdown menu is used to select the Point layer, which contains the field measurement data needed for further analysis.

Finally, we select the cable segment shapefile layer from the third dropdown menu, which will serve as the condition layer for our selection. With five segment layers loaded in the Layers panel, we'll begin by choosing the first one.

Fig.8 The cable segment shapefile layer is selected as the condition layer from the third dropdown menu, with the first segment chosen for the selection process.

Fig.9 After clicking on 'Select,' no point elements are highlighted, despite their apparent proximity to the polyline segments. This indicates that the points do not actually lie directly on the polylines.

We then click on 'Select.'

However, despite the point elements appearing to lie on the polyline segments, none of the points are selected.

This is because they aren't precisely positioned on the polyline. By zooming in closely, we can see that the point features are not exactly aligned with the polyline.

In Fig. 10 and Fig.11, the misalignment is clearly visible, as only the two layers involved in the selection process remain enabled, making it easier to see that the points do not align with the polyline.

Fig.10 The misalignment is clearly visible, as only the two layers involved in the selection process remain enabled. This highlights that the point features do not align with the polyline segments.

Fig.11 The misalignment is further illustrated here for demonstration purposes, emphasizing that the entire polyline feature exhibits this discrepancy.

In situations like this, we would typically use the 'Snap by Layer' function, which allows us to resnap the polyline vertices to the points based on a defined proximity. However, for demonstration purposes, we'll go ahead and repeat the selection process with the third segment layer from the Layers list.

Once again, we open the 'Select by Layer' dialog and set the same options as before. The only difference this time is that we'll choose the third segment from the list for the third option.

Fig.12 The 'Select by Layer' dialog is opened again, with the same settings as before, but this time the third segment from the list is selected as the condition layer.

We click on 'Select,' and right away, the points are selected and highlighted on the Graphics panel. Additionally, all selected points appear in the 'Selected Elements' panel.

Fig.13 Upon clicking 'Select,' the relevant points are immediately highlighted on the Graphics panel, and all selected points are listed in the 'Selected Elements' panel.

We can either review each point one by one or export all of them into a separate layer for further processing.

Fig.14 Users can either examine each selected point individually or export all of them into a new layer for further analysis and processing.

We decide to export all the selected points into a new separate layer using the 'Selected Elements in New Layer' function.

Fig.15 The selected points are exported into a new separate layer using the 'Selected Elements in New Layer' function, allowing for further processing and analysis.

Once the new layer is created with only the filtered and selected points based on specific criteria, we can easily export the layer's coordinates and attributes as

separate CSV files. To do this, simply click on the 'Coordinates to CSV' or 'Attributes to CSV' option found in the 'Element Data' toolbox.

Fig.16 Once the new layer containing the filtered and selected points is created, users can export the coordinates and attributes as separate CSV files by clicking on the 'Coordinates to CSV' or 'Attributes to CSV' options in the 'Element Data' toolbox.

With this, we've successfully completed the procedure.

Fig.17 The procedure has been completed.